

Instructions *[delete before sending the brief to the Fire SCOUT Coordinator!]*

This is the template that Fire SCOUT National Liaisons shall use to summarize information about wildfires in their country of responsibility. Text highlighted with green shall be replaced with actual information. National Liaisons are responsible for ensuring that the provided information is accurate. The Fire Brief document shall be saved as a PDF file with the following name “NERO_Fire_Brief_Year_Country_Event-name.pdf, (e.g., NERO_Fire_Brief_2024_Greece_Nea-Santa.pdf).

NERO Fire Brief

Summary	
[replace with your own summary – max 200 words]	
Late in the afternoon of Saturday 3 August 2024, a wildfire ignited at a forested area near the village of Nea Santa in Rhodope, Northern Greece. Assisted by southerly winds, the fire spread rapidly upslope, burning across very dense and very dry shrubs mixed with pines. Prolonged drought in the area contributed to the availability of dead fuels while the significant lack of atmospheric moisture on the day of ignition enhanced the intensity of burning. Temporarily, the fire exhibited the development of pyroconvection, manifested through the formation of a pyrocumulus (pyroCu) cloud on top of the rising plume. Atmospheric conditions were indeed favorable for the occurrence of pyroconvection: very dry and hot conditions near the surface, intensifying combustion, and moist air advection aloft, enhancing plume development.	
Date and Time	e.g., 3 August 2024, 14:00 UTC
Wildfire Event Name	e.g., Nea Santa Wildfire
Location	e.g., Greece, Rhodope, Nea Santa (include at least country and NUTS3 regional unit, optionally, include nearest town/city/village)
Current Size (ha)	1,500 (leave blank if not available)
Type	Ground fire or Surface fire or Crown fire
Weather Influence	Wind-driven fire or Plume-dominated fire

Fuels	Indicate dominant fuel type that is burning (e.g., grass, shrubs, forest, etc.)
Elevation (m asl)	300
Observed Fire Behavior	Report information relevant to the behavior of the fire (e.g., high fire rate of spread, pyroconvection, fire whirls, spotting, mass ignition, whole column rotation, etc.)
Other Information	Include here any links to any other sources of information for the event